

26 - Improving L2 Reading Efficiency Through Chunk-Based Reading: An Eye-Tracking Investigation

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of chunk-based reading and gaze fixation training on L2 English reading speed and comprehension. Chunk reading, which involves processing text in meaningful multiword units, has been widely recognized for enhancing fluency and comprehension. This research hypothesizes that training learners to fixate their gaze on chunk centers can improve reading efficiency by enabling the processing of chunks as unified units. Using an eye-tracking tool, 42 Japanese university students of varying English proficiency (CEFR A2 and B1) participated in a controlled experiment. Participants completed reading tasks with and without chunk-focused training, and their eye movements and reading outcomes were analyzed. Results indicate that lower-proficiency learners (A2) benefited most, showing significant reductions in eye fixations, faster reading speeds, and improved comprehension post-training. In contrast, higher-proficiency learners (B1) displayed minimal improvement, suggesting chunk-based strategies are particularly effective for foundational language processing. Findings highlight the pedagogical potential of integrating eye movement strategies into L2 instruction, particularly for less proficient learners. These results offer practical insights for optimizing L2 reading strategies and underscore the need for tailored approaches based on learner proficiency.

Keywords: Chunk-based reading, Gaze fixation training, L2 reading comprehension, Eye-tracking technology, Proficiency-based strategies

1. Introduction

Chunk reading, also known as slash or phrase reading, involves reading a passage by dividing it into meaningful multiword units of information that are manageable at a single time (Miller, 1956). Chunking divides a sentence into smaller, meaningful units, comprising several words that form a cohesive word group (Nation, 2011) or meaningful phrase (Kadota, 2001). Due to its potential to improve reading and listening fluency, L2 learning settings have widely adopted this strategy.

In chunk reading, readers segment sentences into meaningful units by visually "slashing" or breaking them down. These chunks typically contain seven plus or minus two words, a concept famously described as the "magic number" (Miller, 1956), or represent lexical bundles that can be spoken within a two-second span (Baddeley, 1992, 2002). Numerous studies have revealed chunk reading as a key facilitator of fluency (Le & Nguyen, 2014; Yamashita & Ichikawa, 2010). As Nation (2011) argue, chunk reading enables learners to process texts in multi-word units, reducing the number of eye fixations and accelerating reading speed (Sutz, 2009).

Beyond improving speed, chunk reading has also been associated with enhanced reading comprehension (Pulido, 2021; Yubune, 2010). By reducing the cognitive load on working memory, chunk reading allows readers to allocate more cognitive resources to comprehension. This, in turn, strengthens inferencing and predictive reading strategies, leading to more effective overall reading (Anderson, 1999).

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Additionally, chunk reading may enhance listening skills (Yubune, 2010), which further reinforces its value for language learning. Moreover, successful reading experiences foster higher self-efficacy among learners (Samuels, 2008), promoting sustainable, motivated learning.

Despite these documented benefits, several key challenges remain unaddressed in the current literature. One persistent issue is how to effectively train learners in chunk reading. For instance, L2 learners whose first language (L1) differs structurally from English, such as Japanese learners, often struggle with chunk-based reading due to differences in word order (Hijikata, 2005). Another challenge involves teaching learners to identify and process chunks as cohesive units. While some learners may naturally develop a visual scanning pattern conducive to chunk reading, others require explicit instruction on how to visually group chunks (Rayner, 1998).

We need further research to understand the individual components of chunk reading and its varied efficacy among learners. As previous studies suggest (Wood, 2007), chunk reading may not be equally effective for all learners, and individual differences may influence the success of this strategy. Therefore, our present study aims to explore methods for training L2 learners in shifting their visual scanning patterns to facilitate chunk reading. Additionally, it seeks to investigate the individual factor that may impact the efficacy of chunk reading as a L2 learning strategy. Based on the above discussion, this study poses the following research questions. (RQ1) Does training with a chunk reading tool designed to reduce eye fixations lead to a measurable decrease in the number of eye fixations during reading among L2 learners? (RQ2) After undergoing chunk-reading training, do L2 learners demonstrate improved reading speed and enhanced reading comprehension compared to their performance prior to training? (RQ3) Does L2 proficiency influence the effect of chunk reading training on reducing eye fixations during L2 reading?

2. Method

2.1 Participants

A total of forty-two Japanese university students participated in the study. Twenty-one students from a university of science and technology (α), whereas an additional 21 students from another science-focused university (β). Participation was entirely voluntary, and compensation was provided for the time dedicated to the study. The research was approved by the research ethics board of both universities, and all participants have signed the consent form. The participants demonstrated varying English proficiency levels: those from the university α were at the CEFR B1 level, as indicated by their TOEFL ITP[®] test scores. In contrast, the participants from the university β demonstrated an average proficiency level of A2, as evidenced by their TOEIC[®] L&R scores. Furthermore, all participants completed the EF SET, a free English proficiency test, prior to the experiment. The mean score for the university α with A2 level was 68.9 and S.E. was 2.9, while that of the other university with B1 was 55.1 and S.E. was 2.8.

2.2 Treatment

The participants were instructed in chunk reading with the aid of a computer-based reading aid tool designed to minimize the number of eye fixations per chunk. The tool displayed passages in consecutive chunks, with the center of each text chunk on the screen (see to Figure 1 for clarification). The participants were instructed to focus their attention on the center of each chunk and to move their eye gaze steadily downward as additional chunks presented. By shifting the participants' reading strategy from word-by-word reading to chunk-based reading, this design aimed to enhance reading comprehension by reducing the eye fixation durations.

Figure 1 - Reading aid tool

For the treatment, three passages were selected from Nation's (2018) book. The three passages (thereafter, passage 1, 2 or 3) had the same word count and vocabulary level, designed for reading at a rapid pace. The passages addressed scholarly topics, but we selected two that were less directly related to scientific or technological subjects to prevent the participants from relying on their prior knowledge of the subject to answer comprehension questions. The participants had to read the entire passage to correctly answer the questions. One passage was read before and during treatment, while the other passage was read just after the treatment. The order of the passages was counterbalanced.

2.3 Procedure

Participants visited the author's office (university a) or the experimental room (university b) at their respective universities, where the research setup was the same: each room was equipped with a 32-inch computer screen displaying each reading passage, a Windows notebook with the chunk-reading aid tool, and Tobii Pro Glasses 3 for eye tracking, which was connected to a separate Windows PC to record eye movement data.

Participants sat on the front of the display with a resolution of 3840×2160. We conducted the calibration of the Tobii Glasses3 prior to the experiment. The experiment had four phases. First, the subjects read either passage 1 or 2 (We will refer to this as Reading 1). After reading, they completed a 10-question test related to the passage they read. Secondly, they utilized the tool to practice chunk-based reading using the reading passage they read in Reading 1. Third, the participants read either passage 1 or 2 they did not read in Reading 1 (Reading 2). Upon completion of this reading, they took a 10-question test related to the passage they had just completed. Finally, they read passage 3 (Reading 3). After finishing this reading, they took a 5-question test related to the reading they completed..

3. Hypotheses

Training with a chunk reading tool is hypothesized to have the following effects.

1. Training with a chunk reading tool will help the participants reduce in the number of their eye fixations during reading.
2. After training, the participants will exhibit improved reading speed and comprehension compared to their pre-training performance.
3. The L2 proficiency influences the effect of chunk reading training on reducing eye fixations during L2 reading at both universities.

4. Results

4.1 Reading time

To assess the reading time, we conducted a two-way repeated-measures ANOVA (Alpha level is 0.05). Figure 2 shows the results of the reading time. Regarding the reading times, significant main effects were revealed in the reading factor ($F(2, 60) = 5.812, p < 0.01, \eta^2 = .098$). There is marginally interaction effect between readings \times universities ($F(2, 60) = 2.58, p < 0.10, \eta^2 = .003$). We conducted multiple comparisons with the Holm methods that show no significant difference is found in the reading factor within univ. a ($F(2, 60) = .815, p = .448, \eta^2 = .026$) and significant differences were found in the reading factor within univ. b ($F(2, 60) = 7.440, p < 0.01, \eta^2 = .199$). On the other hand, significant differences were found in the reading factor within univ. b: reading 1 > reading 2 ($p < 0.05$) and reading1 > reading2 ($p < 0.01$). No significance was found between reading 1 and reading 2 ($p = .635$). Thus, Prediction 2 was partially supported.

Figure 2 - Result of reading time

4.2 Question score

To align the scores with the other readings, we doubled the results from Reading 3. We conducted a two-way repeated-measures ANOVA (Alpha level is 0.05) to assess the question score. Figure 3 shows the results of the question score. Regarding the reading times, significant main effects were revealed in the university factor $F(2, 60)=23.461, p<0.01, \eta^2=.136$. There is no interaction effect. Thus, Prediction 2 was not supported.

Figure 3 - Result of question score

4.3 Eye tracker data

Tobii Pro Lab software enabled the projection of gaze data onto snapshots of English text from the gaze and video data recorded with Tobii Glasses 3 (Figure 4). We projected the fixation points onto a 1920x1080 image and analyzed the gaze data based on accurate projection calculations.

Figure 4 - Fixation data projection

Chillies
 Chillies come in many shapes and sizes, from the tiny bird's eye chillies which are hot enough to burn your mouth, to larger milder varieties. A good rule is the smaller the hotter. Be careful of the chillies that are bright red and only one or two centimetres long. Chillies are the fruit of plants which belong to the Capsicum family. They originated on the American continent where they have been an important part of the diet for approximately 9,500 years. Chillies may have been the first crop to be grown for human consumption in Central and South America, according to evidence from pre-historic sites in Ecuador that date back 8,000 years.
 When Christopher Columbus arrived in America in 1492, he came across the fruit and called them chilli peppers because they were hot to the taste like the black and white pepper already known in Europe. Unlike the pepper used in Europe, however, chilli peppers were cheap. In 15th century Europe, black pepper was so expensive it was used as money in some countries. After Christopher Columbus introduced chillies to Europe they became highly prized for flavouring food. They were also used in medicine to relieve pain. Chillies spread to Asia, South America, Africa, Europe, Portugal and Arab traders.
 Nowadays, there are probably 400 different kinds of chillies produced around the world with India being the world's largest producer, consumer and exporter. This is not surprising for anyone who has eaten a hot Indian curry. However, India is not necessarily the home of the hottest chilli. The title of hottest chilli ever grown is hotly contested by many countries such as Britain, Mexico and Trinidad as well as India.
 But how can the hotness of chillies be accurately measured? In 1912, an American chemist called Wilbur Scoville invented a scale which measures the concentration of heat producing chemicals in chillies. He originally developed the scale by tasting, but now computers can do the job more accurately. The mildest chilli, the sweet green pepper used in salads is rated as 1 unit. In 2012, the hottest chilli ever recorded was rated at over 2,000,000 Scoville units. Chillies of this strength cannot be eaten. They are classed as weapons-grade and they are used in the pepper sprays that police use to fight crime, control violent crowds and stop criminals.

We use the participants' gaze fixation duration from these projected eye tracker data. Figure 5 shows an example of fixation space. The text (680 × 1080 pixels) is divided into five predefined spaces (136 pixels tall, 1080 pixels wide). We obtained the fixation duration of each Space by using Tobii Pro Lab and performed chi-squared test of independence between each university and space condition. The tests revealed significant differences between universities and readings. Tables 2 and 3 show the results of fixation duration at in each space and readings in each university.

Figure 5 - Five spaces of display

Tables 1 and 2 present the observed frequency and adjusted residual for the tests, respectively. If the adjusted residual score for a specific subgroup is greater than 1.96, the subgroup differs significantly ($p < 0.05$) from the overall group percentage. The tests revealed no significant difference between the readings and spaces in univ. a students ($\chi^2(8) = 10.646, df = 8, p = .223, Cramer's V = .025$). Conversely, the tests revealed significant differences between behaviors and spaces in univ. b students ($\chi^2(8) = 122.350, df = 8, p < 0.01, Cramer's V = .007$). Furthermore, the tests revealed significant differences between universities and spaces in reading 1 ($\chi^2(8) = 15.628, df = 8, p < 0.01, Cramer's V = .004$), in reading 2 ($\chi^2(8) = 79.820, df = 8, p < 0.01, Cramer's V = .117$) and in reading 3 ($\chi^2(8) = 75.533, df = 8, p < 0.01, Cramer's V = .119$). Given these findings, prediction 1 was partially supported, while prediction 3 was supported.

Table 1 - Eye tracker result (participants × spaces in each university)

	A	B	C	D	E
(a) Univ. α					
Reading1	663.150 1.983*	939.421 -1.181	943.800 0.009	942.696 -0.386	514.089 -0.169
Reading2	364.130 -1.876	601.828 0.070	601.879 0.741	622.497 1.659	306.876 -1.095
Reading3	322.976 -0.320	522.887 1.301	477.465 -0.795	472.216 -1.309	286.859 1.357
(b) Univ. β					
Reading1	715.837 4.541**	1197.705 5.102**	1188.451 -9.899**	982.477 0.467	583.647 2.047*
Reading2	430.009 -1.681	665.523 -5.735**	1170.796 6.294**	708.895 0.348	394.347 -0.132
Reading3	384.146 -3.247**	753.246 0.250	1081.310 4.414**	653.806 -0.862	346.247 -2.099*

Fixation duration and adjusted residual [sec] (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$)

Table 2 - Eye tracker result (participants × spaces in each reading)

	A	B	C	D	E
(a) Reading1					
Univ. α	663.150 1.563	939.421 -2.359*	943.800 -2.029*	942.696 2.795**	514.089 0.474
Univ. β	715.837 -1.563	1197.705 2.359*	1188.451 2.029*	982.477 -2.795**	583.647 -0.474
(b) Reading2					
Univ. α	364.130 2.015*	601.828* 4.002**	601.879 -8.779**	622.497 3.517**	306.876 0.684
Univ. β	430.009 -2.015*	665.523 -4.002**	1170.796 8.779**	708.895 -3.517**	394.347 -0.684
(c) Reading3					
Univ. α	322.976 3.739**	522.887 1.421	477.465 -8.324**	472.216 2.055*	286.859 3.309**
Univ. β	384.146 -3.739**	753.246 -1.421	1081.310 8.324**	653.806 -2.055*	346.247 -3.309**

Fixation duration and adjusted residual [sec] (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$)

5. Discussion

This study validated the effect of chunk-based reading training using eye-tracking technology to monitor changes in eye movements and reading performance. Additionally, this study examined L2 proficiency differences by comparing the students from two universities at varying L2 proficiency levels (B1 and A2). The results of the reading time analysis indicated chunk-based reading training contributed to lower proficiency learners, whereas no change was observed in higher proficiency ones. This may indicate that higher proficiency learners already had already developed a well-established approach to reading, whereas lower-proficiency learners are less accustomed to reading English texts. Consequently, the chunk-based reading training may prove beneficial for the low-proficiency learners. However, no significant differences were identified between the universities or reading levels with respect to the question score results. This suggests that there is no inherent correlation between reading speed

improvement and content comprehension. The eye-tracker data indicates that more proficient learners do not show a fixation bias toward specific points in the passages and may be segmenting sentences appropriately as they read. While overall fixation time appears to decrease from Reading 2 onwards, no significant difference was observed. An increase in reading speed is likely to be attributed to participants' constant exposure to English passages during the experiment. In contrast, before the chunk-based reading training, the less proficient learners exhibited the tendency to fixate at the beginning of sentences, which may reflect a common tendency among beginners to start reading from the left edge of the page. Following the training, however, their fixation points were more concentrated in the center of the text, suggesting that the chunk-based reading training helped participants to consciously control their gaze.

Figure 6 Result histograms of fixation duration [sec] in each condition

One limitation of this study is that the chunk-based reading training session was only administered once and for a relatively short period of time. A longer training period may also prove beneficial for higher-

proficiency L2 learners. Furthermore, the fatigue experienced by participants during the hour-long experiment may have influenced their comprehension, particularly in the second half of the session, which included Readings 2 and 3. Despite this limitation, the study provides valuable pedagogical insights for implementing second language reading strategies across diverse contexts. The approach of segmenting a text into manageable chunks and presenting these chunks in a centred format is straightforward and can be easily implemented using computers, mobile devices, or even on paper. Future research will be instrumental in refining and developing more versatile and effective L2 reading strategies.

6. Conclusion

This study aims to verify the effectiveness of chunk-based L2 reading and eye movement and fixation training with the use of eye-tracking technology and to examine its influence on L2 proficiency. Based on the findings above, we will provide the responses to each research question (RQ). With regard to RQ1, no notable reduction in eye fixations after the training was observed. However, the learners with lower proficiency levels demonstrated a decrease in eye-fixations during reading after utilizing the training tool, and successfully centralized their eye gaze in the centre of each chunk. Therefore, RQ 1 was partially confirmed. In RQ2, the impact of the chunk reading training was observed only in the context of enhanced reading speed for the lower proficiency learners, with no observable effect on reading comprehension or for those with higher proficiency. The findings indicate that centralizing eye gaze may facilitate reading speed, although this does not be found in every learner. Lower proficiency learners may particularly benefit from the chunk reading training. Therefore, RQ 2 was also partially supported. The findings related to RQ3 demonstrate that lower proficiency (A2) learners significantly embraced the advantage of the eye-fixation training for chunk reading, as evidenced by a reduction in their eye fixations, which resulted in faster reading speed. Hijikata (2005) asserted the efficacy of the chunk reading strategy for intermediate L2 learners. However, this study refined that claim by demonstrating that lower-intermediate learners could derive greater benefit from the training and achieve superior performance.

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